
A Composite Score for Quality Filtering of VCF files

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This document shows how to set the cut-off values for the quality scores QUAL and GQ according to the desired minimum probability that the calls in our VCF file are correct.

1 VCF files

A VCF file contains only the variants in which the subject has at least one allele different from the reference allele. It has been calculated that this number is between 4.1 million to 5.0 million when we consider both SNPs and short indels of a whole genome, see par. “A typical genome” of (1): about 0.1-0.2% of the total 3.2 billion base pairs. This means that a VCF file generated from whole genome sequencing (WGS) must have a length of about 4.5 million lines, while a VCF file from whole exome sequencing will have about $30 \cdot 10^6 \cdot \frac{0.2}{100} = 60 \cdot 10^3$ (while in fact, it is a bit more than that, because the calculation was based on whole genome). For a complete guide to VCF file version 4.2, see the following pdf:

<https://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/VCFv4.2.pdf>

2 Quality control on VCF files

Before any downstream analysis of our VCF files, it is recommended to filter out variants with low confidence, to maximize retained signal while minimizing systematic error. The VCF format provides several indexes to check for the quality of each call. If we define the two events:

Eq. 1 $E_H = \text{the call is not a variant (it is homozygous – reference genotype)}$

Eq. 2 $E_W = \text{the genotype called is wrong}$

then the VCF format provides for each call the two following parameters:

Eq. 3 $QUAL = -10 \log_{10} P(E_H) \Leftrightarrow P(E_H) = 10^{-\frac{QUAL}{10}}$

Eq. 4 $GQ = -10 \log_{10} P(E_W|E_H^C) \Leftrightarrow P(E_W|E_H^C) = 10^{-\frac{GQ}{10}}$

We want the probabilities $P(E_H), P(E_W|E_H^C)$ to be the lowest possible. The two parameters as a function of the probability have the same plot and in Figure 3 you see QUAL as a function of $P(E_H)$: if we want the probability that the call is not a variant to be below 0.01 (99% probability that it is a variant), then we must ask that $QUAL \geq 20$. For $QUAL \geq 30$ we have that the probability that the call is in fact a variant is ≥ 0.999 . The same applies to GQ.

The other parameter that could be checked for is the depth of the reading at each locus, indicated as DP in a VCF file.

3 SNPfiltR

SNPfiltR is a R package that offers the possibility of filtering VCF files with respect to GQ and DP. It can be used both on a single subject and on a population, in the latter case it can be used to detect and filter missing values too (2). SNPfiltR, in turn, uses the package VcfR to convert VCF files into R objects (3). To use these packages you need to write in the R studio console the command:

```
install.packages("SNPfiltR")
```

You can now upload your VCF file (you don't need to unzip them, GZ is accepted) and you will be able to plot the histograms for the distribution of DP and GQ among your variants and filter them by selecting a GQ and a DP cut-off (see the R script below). In our case, the distribution of DP for the SNVs is the one in Figure 1. The distribution for GQ among SNVs and indels can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Distribution of DP among the SNVs. On the left, we have a detail of the distribution for $DP < 25$.

Figure 2. Distribution of GQ among the SNVs (left) and the indels (right).

```
# file name: quality_control
#
# This script run ana analysis the the VCF files by using the pakage SNPfilter
# which can be installed by the command install.packages("SNPfiltR")
#
library(SNPfiltR)
library(vcfR)
#
# We read the VCF file (you can directly upload the GZ file)
#
vcfR <- read.vcfR("paolo_maccallini_snp.vcf.gz")
#
# We visualize the distributions with respect to GQ and DP
#
hard_filter(vcfR=vcfR)
#
# We filter out variants with DP < 5 and GQ < 30
#
vcfR<-hard_filter(vcfR=vcfR, depth = 5, gq = 30)
#
# We write out the filtered VCF file (it is a GZ file!)
```

```
#
vcfR::write.vcf(vcfR, "paolo_maccallini_snp_filtered.gz")
#
# We repeat the steps for the indel VCF file
#
vcfR <- read.vcfR("paolo_maccallini_indel.vcf.gz")
hard_filter(vcfR=vcfR)
vcfR<-hard_filter(vcfR=vcfR, depth = 5, gq = 30)
vcfR::write.vcf(vcfR, "paolo_maccallini_indel_filtered.gz")
```


Figure 3. The score QUAL as a function of the probability that the variant is not a variant.

If we now filter out the SNVs with GQ < 30 and DP < 5, we have the following results:

```
8.69% of genotypes fall below a read depth of 5 and were converted to NA
8.47% of genotypes fall below a genotype quality of 30 and were converted to NA
```

We can then save the filtered VCF file, where the variants filtered out appear as missing values. If we apply the same filtering to the indels we get:

```
12% of genotypes fall below a read depth of 5 and were converted to NA
13.82% of genotypes fall below a genotype quality of 30 and were converted to NA
```

We can now generate the filtered VCF file for indels. VCF files generated by SNPfiltR are GZ files, keep that in mind and add the extension .gz to their names.

4 A composite score

Let us consider again the events in Eq. 1, Eq. 2, and define the following event:

Eq. 5 $E_C = E_W^C = \text{the genotype called is correct}$

Then we can write according to the Byes formula that

$$P(E_W|E_H^C) = \frac{P(E_W \cap E_H^C)}{P(E_H^C)} = \frac{P(E_C^C \cap E_H^C)}{P(E_H^C)} = \frac{P((E_C \cup E_H)^C)}{P(E_H^C)} = \frac{1 - P(E_C \cup E_H)}{1 - P(E_H)}$$

Since $P(E_C \cup E_H) = P(E_C) + P(E_H) - P(E_C \cap E_H)$ we have

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad P(E_W|E_H^C) = \frac{1 - P(E_C) - P(E_H) + P(E_C \cap E_H)}{1 - P(E_H)} = 1 - \frac{P(E_C) - P(E_C \cap E_H)}{1 - P(E_H)}$$

But when E_H is true, then the call is not a variant and so it has been wrongly genotyped in order to be included in the VCF file, so E_C must be false. On the other hand, when E_C is true, then E_H . So E_C, E_H can't be true at the same time (while they can be false at the same time). This means that $E_H \cap E_C = \emptyset$ and we can write $P(E_C \cup E_H) = P(E_C) + P(E_H)$. Hence, we have

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad P(E_W|E_H^C) = 1 - \frac{P(E_C)}{1 - P(E_H)} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad P(E_C) = \left(1 - P(E_W|E_H^C)\right)(1 - P(E_H)) = \left(1 - 10^{-\frac{GQ}{10}}\right)\left(1 - 10^{-\frac{QUAL}{10}}\right)$$

The plot of $P(E_C)$ as a function of $P(E_W|E_H^C), P(E_H)$ can be seen on the left half of Figure 4. On the right, $P(E_C)$ is plotted as a function of $QUAL, GQ$. The former surface seems a plane, but it is a hyperbolic paraboloid, as can be easily shown: if we adopt the symbology in (4) we consider the generic quadratic and its associated matrix:

$$a_{11}x^2 + a_{22}y^2 + a_{33}z^2 + 2a_{12}xy + 2a_{13}xz + 2a_{23}yz + 2a_{01}x + 2a_{02}y + 2a_{03}z + a_{00} = 0$$

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{00} & a_{10} & a_{20} & a_{30} \\ a_{10} & a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{20} & a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{30} & a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

Then, if we put $x \triangleq P(E_H), y \triangleq P(E_W|E_H^C), z \triangleq P(E_C)$, we can write Eq. 8 as the quadratic:

$$xy - x - y - z + 1 = 0$$

and therefore its associated matrix is

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Then we have $|A| = \frac{1}{16}, |A_{234,234}| = 0$, so we must conclude that the surface on the left of Figure 4 is a hyperbolic paraboloid. If we consider both Eq. 7 and Eq. 9 (see below) we can now find the

combinations of values for $P(E_W|E_H^C)$, $P(E_H)$ and QUAL, GQ respectively, for any fixed value of $P(E_C)$, as shown in Figure 5.

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad 10^{-\frac{GQ}{10}} = 1 - \frac{P(E_C)}{1 - 10^{-\frac{QUAL}{10}}} \Leftrightarrow GQ = -10 \log_{10} \left(1 - \frac{P(E_C)}{1 - 10^{-\frac{QUAL}{10}}} \right)$$

Figure 4. Plots of $P(E_C)$ as a function of $P(E_W|E_H^C)$, $P(E_H)$ (left) and of QUAL, GQ (right).

Figure 5. GQ as a function of QUAL, for different values of $P(E_C)$.

Note that for Eq. 7 to be verified it must be

$$0 \leq 1 - \frac{P(E_C)}{1 - P(E_H)} \leq 1 \Leftrightarrow -1 \leq -\frac{P(E_C)}{1 - P(E_H)} \leq 0 \Leftrightarrow 1 \geq \frac{P(E_C)}{1 - P(E_H)} \geq 0 \Leftrightarrow$$

Eq. 10 $P(E_H) \leq 1 - P(E_C)$

This disequality can be translated into the homologous condition for Eq. 9:

$$10^{-\frac{QUAL}{10}} \leq 1 - P(E_C) \Leftrightarrow -QUAL \leq 10 \log_{10}(1 - P(E_C)) \Leftrightarrow$$

Eq. 11 $QUAL \geq -10 \log_{10}(1 - P(E_C)) = \log_{10} \frac{1}{(1 - P(E_C))^{10}}$

So, for instance, if we request $P(E_C) > 0.98$ we can set $QUAL > 20$ and $GQ > 20$; for $QUAL > 25$ and $GQ > 30$ we have $P(E_C) > 0.996$; and so forth. This figure can be used to set $QUAL$, GQ according to the desired minimum value for $P(E_C)$.

4.1 Script

Below you find the Octave script that generates Figure 3, Figure 4, and Figure 5.

```
% file name: quality_scores
clear all
close all
%
% we plot QUAL as a function of P(E_H)
%
p = [0:0.0002:0.03];
for i = 1:length(p)
    score(i) = -10*log10(p(i));
endfor
f = 1;
figure(f)
plot(p, score, '-k', 'linewidth', 1.5)
grid on
grid minor on
xlabel('P({E_H})','fontsize',15);
ylabel('QUAL','fontsize',15);
hold on
plot([0.001, 0.001], [0., score(2)], '--r', 'linewidth', 1)
hold on
plot([0.01, 0.01], [0., score(2)], '--r', 'linewidth', 1)
axis([0,max(p),0,score(2)])
%
% we plot P(E_C) as a function of P(E_H) and P(E_W|(E_H)^C)
%
f = f+1;
figure(f)
for i=1:length(p)
    for j=1:length(p)
        P_C(i,j) = ( 1- p(i) )*( 1- p(j) );
    endfor
endfor
array = ([transpose([0.6:0.01:1]),transpose([0.6:0.01:1]),transpose([0.6:0.01:1])]);
surf(p(1:5:length(p)),p(1:5:length(p)),P_C(1:5:length(p),1:5:length(p)))
```

```

colormap (array)
grid on
grid minor on
xlabel('P(E_{H})','fontsize',15);
ylabel('P(E_{W}|E_{H}^{C})','fontsize',15);
zlabel('P(E_{C})','fontsize',15);
axis ('square')
%
% we plot P(E_C) as a function of QUAL and GQ
%
f = f+1;
figure(f)
GQ = [18:1:40];
QUAL = GQ;
for i=1:length(GQ)
    for j=1:length(QUAL)
        P_C2(i,j) = ( 1- 10^(-GQ(i)/10) )*( 1- 10^(-QUAL(j)/10) );
    endfor
endfor
array = ([transpose([0.6:0.01:1]),transpose([0.6:0.01:1]),transpose([0.6:0.01:1])]);
surf(QUAL,GQ,P_C2)
colormap (array)
grid on
grid minor on
xlabel('GQ','fontsize',15);
ylabel('QUAL','fontsize',15);
zlabel('P(E_{C})','fontsize',15);
axis ('square')
%
% we plot GQ as a function of QUAL for several values of P(E_C)
%
f = f + 1;
figure(f)
pc = [0.98, 0.990, 0.992, 0.994, 0.996, 0.998, 0.999];
legend_c = cell(length(pc));
strleg = 'P(E_C) = ';
for i=1:length(pc)
    clear QUAL
    clear GQ
    Qinf = log10(1/(1-pc(i))^10);
    Qsup = 45;
    Qdelta = (Qsup - Qinf)/20;
    QUAL = [Qinf:Qdelta:Qsup];
    for j=1:length(QUAL)
        GQ(i,j) = - 10*log10( 1 - pc(i)/( 1 - 10^( -QUAL(j)/10 ) ) );
    endfor
    legend_c(i) = strcat(strleg, num2str(pc(i)));
    plot(QUAL,GQ(i,:), 'linewidth',1.5)
    hold on
endfor
grid on
grid minor on
xlabel('QUAL','fontsize',15);
ylabel('GQ','fontsize',15);
legend (char(legend_c(1:length(pc))), 'fontsize',15, 'location', 'NORTHWEST')
axis([15,45,15,40])

```

5 Bibliography

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